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Research Article

**STUDY TO ESTIMATE CARDIOVASCULAR RISK AND TO
DETERMINE THE OCCURRENCE OF HYPERTENSION IN
PATIENTS OF LAHORE****Kashmala Jamil¹, Anum Ishfaq², Sundas Nasrullah³**
^{1,2,3}Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore Pakistan**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of our study was to estimate cardiovascular risk and to determine the occurrence of hypertension in patients of Lahore.

Study design: A cross sectional study.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from October, 2019 to September, 2020.

Methodology: In our present study 2336 patients were enrolled. We collected data from patients of either age and gender or seeking their medical consultation routine. We used Seventh Report of Joint National Committee (JNC 7) guidelines to find out the staging and diagnosis of hypertension. On the basis of laboratory and non-laboratory parameters we calculated gender wise Framingham score. SPSS v.20 was used for the analysis of data.

Results: In our present study 2336 patients were selected and the occurrence prehypertension were in 31.4% of patients and hypertension were in 51.5% of patients. Coprevalent hypertension and diabetes were found in 501 patients. For cardiovascular disease (CVD) we calculate ten-year Framingham scores with the use of non-laboratory parameters and this were found in 56% patients (947/1693) age range was greater than or equal to 30 years. Calcium channel blockers and angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors were agents of choice.

Conclusions: At the end of our study, we conclude that the prevalence of hypertension in clinical settings is undesirably high, these patients are at a significant risk of developing cardiovascular disease in Lahore. Medical community and governmental authorities need a concerted effort to address this major health issue. To increase disease awareness and optimize treatments, Current national guidelines need to be harmonized with latest evidence-based guidelines.

Key Words: Physicians, Primary Care, Hypertension

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is an independent risk factor for coronary heart disease, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, and chronic renal failure and a leading cause of cardiovascular (CV) morbidity and mortality [1,2]. Over 2/3rd of patients with hypertension are from developing countries and this is attributed to modern lifestyles and increasing life spans. The global burden of hypertension is predicted to cross 1.5 billion by 2025 [3,4]. Hypertension is widely prevalent in Lahore and the number of cases has doubled from 17% in 1980 to 35% in 2008 [5]. Results from Lahore National Health Survey in the late nineties showed that incidence of hypertension in adults >45 years of age (33%) was twice that in the general population (≥15 years and older; 18%) [6].

In addition, approximately 1/4th of middle-aged adults in Lahore have coronary artery disease and 17% population carries at least two associated risk factors [7,8]. Since hypertension is a progressive disease, early detection and blood pressure control are the keys to reduction in CV risk. Clinical evidence demonstrates that screening for high blood pressure has benefits in reduction of CV events [9]. Guidelines laid down by the 7th report of the Joint National Committee on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC 7) recommends screening individuals ≥18 years of age for hypertension, and evaluating those with hypertension for associated CV risk factors [10]. In recent years, rapid and significant changes in lifestyle practices in Lahore have a direct bearing on CV risk. Consequently, there is an urgent need to determine the burden of hypertension as well as the associated CV risk in Lahorei adults. Risk prediction models are a useful tool in clinical practice to identify, communicate with, and treat high-risk individuals before disease complications set in. Numerous risk factors interact and contribute to the pathology of CV disease. Epidemiological and clinical evidence suggest that translating risk factors into scores can predict an individual's CV risk with a certain amount of accuracy. Risk prediction algorithms such as Framingham Risk Score (FRS), Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation (SCORE), and World Health Organization/International Society of Hypertension (WHO/ISH) score are widely used to identify and manage patients at high CV risk [11,12,13].

The Framingham model employs either laboratory parameters (such as serum lipid levels) or nonlaboratory parameters (such as body mass index and anthropometrics) for calculation of risk score. A comparative study published in the Lancet in 2008 showed that scoring with non-laboratory parameters

not only identifies patients at risk, but also offers the advantages of feasibility and cost-effectiveness [14]. Laboratory investigations in Lahore are generally expensive to conduct and can be an economic strain to a majority of the population, especially those in the low-income strata. Hence, a risk scoring model that combines predictability with practicality and can be used in primary care physicians' (PCP) clinic would be quite useful in CV risk estimation in Lahore.

Focusing on these issues, the primary goal of our study was to assess prevalence of hypertension in general population visiting PCPs for medical consultation. In addition, we also sought to compare non-laboratory-based parameters over standard laboratory parameters in predicting CV risk in adults ≥30 years of age, to stratify our hypertensive patients as per JNC 7 guidelines and to assess the antihypertensive therapy prescribed to them.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from October, 2019 to September, 2020. Study investigators were community-based PCPs from these cities and were randomly selected from the physician database of Sanofi-Aventis Pakistan Ltd. The study was conducted in compliance with all international and applicable guidelines, national laws and regulations of Pakistan. The study was conducted in the ambulatory care setting, at individual outpatient clinics. Adults ≥18 years of age, who were seeking medical consultation with their PCP, irrespective of their hypertension status were included. Patients with a past history of myocardial infarction or objectively confirmed angina pectoris, suspected/known secondary hypertension, or were pregnant, were excluded. Each investigator recruited 20 consecutive patients. Data collected by the investigator at the time of enrolment included patient demographics and anthropometrics, lifestyle choices, CV risk factors and medical history, and two consequent blood pressure recordings taken at the site at a 5-minute interval.

Patients ≥30 years of age were directed to a predetermined laboratory for estimation of serum cholesterol and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). Laboratory tests were conducted by Hospital Clinical Laboratory. Prevalence estimation and staging of hypertension were done using JNC 7 guidelines. Hypertension was characterized as systolic blood pressure (SBP) ≥140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ≥90 mmHg for patients without diabetes, and SBP ≥130 mmHg or DBP ≥80 mmHg for patients with diabetes. For each patient ≥30 years,

Framingham risk scores were calculated (Models A and B, Suppl. Fig. 1 and 2) based on their laboratory and non-laboratory parameters. Scores for each patient were multiplied by a factor of 1.4 as recommended by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in order to make them applicable to the South Asian phenotype [15]. Based on an estimated prevalence of hypertension of 18% with a 1.5% margin of error, 95% confidence level and anticipating 10% data unworthiness (due to incomplete information, missing forms, etc.) a sample size of 2800 patients was required. This sample size also allowed us to meaningfully evaluate CV risk with both Framingham models with a 95% confidence limit and 1.5% margin of error. Differences between scores generated by Model A and B were probed for statistical validity by paired t-test. Patients' scores were also categorized for risk as low (<10%), medium (10%-20%), or high (>20%) and differences in

proportion within each category were compared using Chi-square test. The statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 18 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA)

RESULTS:

The study population comprised 56% males and had an average age of 40.8 ± 13.1 years (Table 1). The proportion of patients ≥ 30 years in the cohort was 72.5% (1693/2336). BMI at 28.2 ± 5.1 kg/m² was marginally higher in this subpopulation, as was the proportion of patients with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m². In patients ≥ 30 years, the proportion of women with BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² was greater than men (78.0% vs. 67.8%). This trend was replicated in the case of prevalence of diabetes i.e. 29.4% (497/1693) patients ≥ 30 years had diabetes and a larger proportion of women presented with diabetes (32.1% versus 26.9% in men).

Table No 01: Gender Distribution According to Study

Gender	Total patients in study		Patients ≥ 30 years of age	
	Qty	% age	Qty	% age
Male	1307	56%	892	52.7%
Female	1029	44%	801	47.3%
Total	2336	100%	1693	100%

As per JNC 7 guidelines, 51.5% (n=1202, 95% CI. 48.6% - 54.4%) of patients in our study had hypertension. Average SBP and DBP in the overall cohort was 137.5 ± 21.1 mmHg and 87.6 ± 11.3 mmHg respectively, and both were marginally higher in patients ≥ 30 years □ SBP: 141.9 ± 20.7 mmHg; DBP: 89.7 ± 10.7 mmHg □.

Table No 02: Calculation of Blood Pressure in mmHg

Blood Pressure	Total patients in study	Patients ≥ 30 years of age
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
SBP	137.5 \pm 21.1	141.9 \pm 20.7
DBP	87.6 \pm 11.3	89.7 \pm 10.7
Hip circumference, in cm	101.0 \pm 14.6	103.6 \pm 14.4
Waist	0.93 \pm 0.10	0.94 \pm 0.10
Ratio (WHR), overall	0.95 \pm 0.09	0.95 \pm 0.09
	0.91 \pm 0.10	0.92 \pm 0.10

The most widely prescribed class of agents was angiotensinogen-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors (in 41% [493/1202] patients). Of the 734 patients in the pre-hypertensive stage, 251 (34.2%) were prescribed antihypertensive agents. Of 139 patients with co-prevalent prehypertension and diabetes, 57% (n=80) were prescribed antihypertensive agents. The agents of choice in patients with coprevalent diabetes and hypertension were ACE inhibitors and beta blockers.

Table No 03: Therapeutic Management According to Stage of Hypertension

Treatment prescribed	Hypertensives without diabetes			Hypertensives with diabetes		
	Qty (%age)			Qty (%age)		
	Prehypertension (734)	Stage I (699)	Stage II (608)	Prehypertension (139)	Stage I (194)	Stage II (182)
Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Inhibitors	67,9.1%	269,38.5%	277,45.6%	30,21.6%	79,40.7%	81,44.5%
Calcium Channel Blockers	53,7.2%	154,22.0%	191,31.4%	22,15.8%	32,16.5%	44,24.2%
Angiotensin Receptor Blockers	45,6.1%	140,20.0%	141,23.2%	21,15.1%	44,22.7%	48,26.4%
Beta Blockers	36,4.9%	113,16.2%	139,22.9%	16,11.5%	54,27.8%	61,33.5%
Diuretics	12,1.6%	68,9.7%	108,17.8%	4,2.9%	29,14.9%	40,22%
Fixed Dose Combination	32,4.4%	60,8.6%	73,12.0%	13,9.4%	24,12.4%	28,15.4%
Others	6,0.8%	21,3.0%	36,5.9%	2,1.4%	7,3.6%	12,6.6%

DISCUSSION:

In this nationwide estimate of the burden of essential hypertension in Lahori adults, we discovered that prevalence of hypertension in outpatient settings is substantially higher than in previous population-based surveys, and every second patient ≥ 18 years of age visiting a primary care physician (PCP) is likely to have high blood pressure. After staging patients' blood pressure as per JNC 7, we determined that only 12.6% of our study population was normotensive and this proportion further decreased to 3.7% in patients with diabetes. Furthermore, analysis of Framingham scores revealed that $>50\%$ of the study population was at a medium-to-high risk of developing CV events within the next 10 years. The rising prevalence of hypertension in Lahore has been attributed to a plethora of factors like genetic predisposition, urbanization, dietary habits, concomitant rise in prevalence of obesity and diabetes, sedentary lifestyles, and lack of health awareness [16,17]. Our estimated prevalence of 51.4% is substantially higher than figures reported from previous studies in Lahore, South Asia, the United States, and Europe. However, we must consider that since our study was conducted in clinical settings, the study cohort could have a higher proportion of hypertensive patients than the general population [18,19,20,21]. Prehypertension is defined as SBP of 120-139 mmHg or DBP of 80-89 mmHg per the JNC 7 guidelines and is a precursor stage to hypertension [22]. Approximately $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ of prehypertensive patients is estimated to progress to hypertensive stage within 4 years. Prehypertension, by itself, is also associated with adverse CV outcomes and progression of diabetes [23,24]. Hence, it becomes imperative to also monitor the prevalence of prehypertension and suggest appropriate intervention as per guidelines. Various elaborate global studies such as the NHANES or a meta-analysis by Guo, et al

estimate the global burden of prehypertension to be 31%-36% [25,26]. Our study population had 31.4% patients in the prehypertensive stage, which corroborates with the global estimate. Additionally, the prevalence of prehypertension in our study is comparable to those estimated from other regional studies in Asia – India, Korea, Japan, China, and Iran [27,28].

The United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study determined that hypertension is comorbid in approximately 70% of patients with diabetes, and is twice as prevalent in patients with diabetes [29]. A sizeable proportion of newly diagnosed diabetes patients have also been shown to have pre-existent hypertension. In our study, approximately $1/5^{\text{th}}$ of the patients ($n=501$, 21.4%; CI: 19.8 – 23.2) had prevalent diabetes and hypertension, and 701 (30.0%, CI: 28.2 – 31.9) patients had hypertension exclusively. The prevalence of diabetes in hypertensive patients was 41.7%. These findings are consistent with the belief that hypertension can worsen diabetic complications and strongly corroborate the association of hypertension and diabetes in CV pathology. Despite proven usefulness of aforementioned risk prediction models, issues that have most likely hindered their routine use in clinical practice at a PCP level in Lahore are awareness of these models among the physicians' community and the need for expensive and time-consuming laboratory tests to implement these. There is limited data on the applicability of these models in a population that is as heterogeneous in terms of ethnicity, lifestyle, socioeconomic status, and genetics, as in Lahore. A recent study that compared these models (FRS, SCORE, and WHO/ISH) in Malaysian population suggests use of FRS for identifying individuals at high risk [30]. In our study, non-laboratory Framingham scores indicated a higher

risk profile in females in comparison with laboratory-based scores, with a paired difference of 3.17 ± 4.27 between the average scores ($p < 0.01$). In contrast, risk profiles were similar for males when either model was used. However, almost a quarter of Lahori women and approximately one-third of Lahori men over the age of 30 years are at a high risk of developing cardiovascular disease within the next 10 years. Thus, our results demonstrate utility of non-laboratory-based Framingham risk scoring for identification of high CV risk individuals in Lahore and validate similar findings from other studies [31,32].

The Lahore Hypertension League has drafted guidelines for therapeutic management of hypertension in Lahore and these are largely based on those laid by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (United Kingdom). These recommend the use of ACE inhibitors, ARBs or CCBs as first line of treatment depending on the patients' age (ACE inhibitors or ARBs for patients < 55 years and CCBs for patients > 55 years) and ethnicity and are in stark contrast with the JNC 7 guidelines which advocate use of thiazide diuretics for lowering BP. In our study we observed an adherence to the Lahore guidelines, since ACE inhibitors were the drugs of choice across the hypertensive fraction of the study cohort. Interestingly, despite 31.4% of the study cohort being pre-hypertensive, we discerned that only 1/3rd of them were prescribed antihypertensive medications. In prehypertensive patients with diabetes, only 57% were prescribed medical intervention. This is indeed alarming since JNC 7 guidelines specify prehypertension with diabetes to be a compelling indication that warrants the use of BP-lowering agents to ameliorate disease progression.

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we conclude that the prevalence of hypertension in clinical settings is undesirably high, these patients are at a significant risk of developing cardiovascular disease in Lahore. Medical community and governmental authorities need a concerted effort to address this major health issue. To increase disease awareness and optimize treatments, Current national guidelines need to be harmonized with latest evidence-based guidelines.

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